

Complexes of Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) with Bis(1,2-diphenyl-1-hydroxyimino-2-ethylidene)- 1,2-diaminobenzene

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A number of complexes of the types, ML ($M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}$), $M(H_2L)X_2$ ($M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}$; $X = Cl^-, Br^-, I^-, ClO_4^-$ or NO_3^-) and Cu_2LX_2 ($X = Cl^-, Br^-, ClO_4^-$, NO_3^-), where $H_2L = \text{bis}(1,2\text{-diphenyl-1-hydroxyimino-2-ethylidene)-1,2-diaminobenzene}$ have been synthesised and characterised on the basis of elemental analyses, magnetic moment, infrared and electronic spectral data.

METAL complexes with dimethylglyoxime (H_2dmg), acetylacetonedioxime (H_2aado) and diacetylazinedioxime (H_2daado) have received special attention¹⁻⁴, as the bis-complexes, such as $M(dmg)_2$, $M(aado)_2$ and $M_2(daado)_2$, simulate as exobidentate and exo-quadridentate ligands, respectively, leading to the formation of binuclear, trinuclear and tetranuclear metal clusters^{5,6}.

In continuation of earlier work in the field⁷, we report herein the isolation and characterisation of 17 complexes with bis(1,2-diphenyl-1-hydroxyimino-2-ethylidene)-1,2-diaminobenzene (hereafter H_2L).

Experimental

1,2-Diaminobenzene was of B.D.H. quality and all other chemicals were of reagent grade.

Preparation of complexes :

$Cu(L)$: 1,2-Diphenyl-1-hydroxyiminoethane-2-one (2.25 g, 0.01 mol) was taken in absolute alcohol and the solution gently warmed. To this solution, cupric acetate monohydrate (2.00 g, 0.01 mol) was added when colour of the solution turned grey. An ethanolic solution of 1,2-diaminobenzene (0.54 g, 0.005 mol) was added to it with constant shaking and the mixture was heated on a water-bath. A green precipitate was obtained whose quantity was found to increase on standing. It was filtered, washed with alcohol and ether.

Cu_2LX_2 ($X = Cl^-, Br^-, ClO_4^-$ or NO_3^-) : To an alcoholic solution of bis(1,2-diphenyl-1-hydroxyimino-2-ethylidene)-1,2-diaminobenzene-copper(II) (2.92 g, 0.005 mol) was added slowly hot alcoholic solution of cupric chloride dihydrate (0.85 g, 0.005

mol) with occasional shaking. A heavy green precipitate so obtained was filtered, washed with a small quantity of ethanol and ether and dried under vacuum.

$M(H_2L)X_2$ ($X = Cl^-, Br^-, I^-, ClO_4^-$ or NO_3^- ; $M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}$) : To an ethanolic solution of the metal salt (0.01 mol), a hot alcoholic solution of 1,2-diphenyl-1-hydroxyiminoethane-2-one (2.25 g, 0.01 mol) was added followed by the addition of an alcoholic solution of 1,2-diaminobenzene (0.54 g, 0.005 mol) with vigorous shaking. Orange, red or dark red crystals separated out on standing were filtered, washed subsequently with alcohol and ether, and dried under vacuum.

The compounds were analysed by the standard procedure⁷. Magnetic moments were determined by Gouy method with $CoHg(SCN)_4$ as the calibrant. The analytical data and colour are recorded in Table 1. Relevant bands in electronic spectra and room temperature magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) values are recorded in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

Ir spectra : The complexes of the type, $M(H_2L)X_2$ show a strong band centered at 3 400 cm^{-1} assigned to ν_{O-H} mode of the N-O-H groups intramolecularly hydrogen bonded^{7,8}, indicating neutral form of the ligand in these complexes. A medium intensity ir band at 1 700 cm^{-1} was observed for $M(H_2L)X_2$ complexes, while for ML and Cu_2LX_2 complexes it disappeared indicating this band probably being due to N-O-H deformation¹⁻⁴. The azomethine and oxime C=N group stretching vibrations at 1 635 and 1 450 cm^{-1}

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND COLOUR OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
		Metal	N	Halogen
CuL	Green	10.61 (10.88)	9.50 (9.61)	—
NiL	Orange red	10.00 (10.19)	9.56 (9.67)	—
CoL	Dark brown	10.15 (10.20)	9.54 (9.95)	—
Cu ₂ LCl ₂	Green	17.56 (17.68)	7.75 (7.80)	9.60 (9.88)
Cu ₂ LBr ₂	Greenish black	15.70 (15.73)	6.91 (6.93)	19.83 (19.82)
Cu ₂ L(NO ₃) ₂	Green	16.44 (16.47)	10.91 (10.89)	—
Cu ₂ L(ClO ₄) ₂	Deep green	15.00 (15.01)	6.65 (6.62)	—
Ni(H ₂ L)Cl ₂	Yellowish red	9.00 (9.04)	8.42 (8.50)	10.89 (10.82)
Ni(H ₂ L)Br ₂	Dark red	7.90 (7.96)	7.52 (7.55)	24.82 (24.79)
Ni(H ₂ L)I ₂	Dark red	7.00 (7.06)	6.65 (6.70)	30.44 (30.42)
Ni(H ₂ L)(NO ₃) ₂	Orange	8.34 (8.36)	11.89 (11.91)	—
Ni(H ₂ L)(ClO ₄) ₂	Red	7.70 (7.56)	7.20 (7.17)	—
Co(H ₂ L)Cl ₂	Light red	9.02 (9.08)	8.40 (8.42)	10.90 (10.91)
Co(H ₂ L)Br ₂	Red	7.95 (8.00)	7.54 (7.56)	—
Co(H ₂ L)I ₂	Brown red	7.10 (7.18)	6.80 (6.84)	—
Co(H ₂ L)(NO ₃) ₂	Orange red	8.42 (8.48)	12.02 (12.09)	—
Co(H ₂ L)(ClO ₄) ₂	Dark red	7.82 (7.84)	7.31 (7.39)	—

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BAND (cm⁻¹) AND MAGNETIC MOMENT VALUES OF Co^{II}, Ni^{II} AND Cu^{II} COMPLEXES

Ni(H ₂ L)X ₂	³ A _{1g} ← ³ B _{1g}	³ E _g ← ³ B _{1g}	³ T _{1g} (P) ← ³ A _{1g}	μ _{eff} B.M.
Ni(H ₂ L)Cl ₂	13 000	18 700	24 700	2.90
Ni(H ₂ L)Br ₂	13 800	18 500	24 800	2.80
Ni(H ₂ L)I ₂	13 900	19 000	24 600	2.80
Ni(H ₂ L)(NO ₃) ₂	13 800	18 500	24 000	2.90
Ni(H ₂ L)(ClO ₄) ₂	14 200	19 000	24 500	2.75
Co(H ₂ L)X ₂	⁴ T _{1g} (P) ← ⁴ T _{1g} (F)	C. T. band		μ _{eff} B.M.
Co(H ₂ L)Cl ₂	16 000		24 000	5.12
Co(H ₂ L)Br ₂	16 100		23 500	5.15
Co(H ₂ L)I ₂	15 200		23 500	5.22
Co(H ₂ L)(NO ₃) ₂	16 100		22 700	5.15
ML	Assignment			μ _{eff} B.M.
CuL	14 000	CuN ₄ ligand field band		1.71
NiL	20 700	¹ A _{1g} ← ¹ A _{1g}		Diamag.
		¹ B _{2g} ← ¹ A _{1g}		
		¹ E _g ← ¹ A _{1g}		
CoL	20 900	³ B _{1g} ← ³ A _{1g}		2.10
Cu ₂ LX ₂	Chromophore			μ _{eff} B.M.
	CuO ₂ X ₂	CuN ₄		
Cu ₂ LCl ₂	12 200	17 500		1.73
Cu ₂ LBr ₂	12 700	17 000		1.70
Cu ₂ L(NO ₃) ₂	12 300	17 400		1.50
Cu ₂ L(ClO ₄) ₂	12 800	18 000		1.55

of free ligand were most perturbed by complexation ($\Delta\nu = 20-30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The ir bands due to phenyl ring systems of the ligand found at 1 590, 1 570, 1 500 and 1 442 cm^{-1} were almost unaffected in the metal complexes. For ML complexes, the high frequencies C—N band shifted to a lower frequency region and the low frequency C—N band suffered a blue-shift. For Cu₂LX₂ (X = Cl⁻, Br⁻) complexes, one band was observed in the low frequency region 450–200 cm^{-1} , viz. at 420 cm^{-1} for Cu₂LCl₂ and at 318 cm^{-1} for Cu₂LBr₂, which could be assigned to terminal $\nu_{\text{Cu-halogen}}$ modes.

Three distinct ir bands appeared in the region 1 100–900 cm^{-1} for the ligand and the complexes, the middle one of which is assigned to $\nu_{\text{N-O}}$. The ligand band at 1 010 cm^{-1} was shifted to the region 1 120–1 090 cm^{-1} in the M(H₂L)X₂ complexes. For the Cu₂LX₂ complex, there was a lowering of frequency of this band to the region 1 040–1 000 cm^{-1} which probably arise⁵ due to the formation of new links between the copper(II) inner-complex (CuL) and copper(II) salts (CuX₂) as shown in structure (1).

(1)

Magnetic moment and electronic spectra : The binuclear Cu₂LX₂ complexes showed μ_{eff} of 1.7 to 1.9 B.M. per copper atom. The electronic spectra of the complexes have been studied in the ligand field region 10 000–25 000 cm^{-1} (Table 2). The spectra of Cu^{II} complexes composed of two broad bands at 12 000–12 700 and 17 000–17 800 cm^{-1} . It would be reasonable to say that the high frequency band arises for the chromophore, CuN₄ in D_{4h} symmetry, and the low frequency band originates from the chromophore, CuO₂X₂ under a lower symmetry such as C₂. A single broad band centred at 14 000 cm^{-1} was observed for the complex CuL having the CuN₄ geometry. The broad band, which shows considerable structure, represents two or three superposed absorptions. The band is comparable both in position and width with the earlier reported planar copper(II) complexes and lead us to believe that all the inner complex salts of copper(II) are essentially square-planar.

The nickel(II) complexes of the type, M(H₂L)X₂ with uncharged ligand, showed μ_{eff} of 2.7–3.1 B.M. at room temperature, suggesting an octahedral arrangement of the ligand atoms around the central nickel(II) ion. The electronic spectra consist of three bands at 13 000–14 000, 20 000 and 24 000

cm^{-1} . The positions, intensities and widths correspond to octahedral nickel(II) with certain amount of tetragonal distortion. The nickel(II) inner complexes were diamagnetic. The electronic spectra consist of a broad band at $20\,000\text{--}22\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The width of the spectra manifests that the band represents a group of two to three transitions under a square-planar environment possessing the chromophore, $\text{NiN}_4^{13,14}$.

$\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{L})\text{X}_2$ complexes have μ_{eff} of 4.9–5.2 B.M. and exhibit a multiplet band structure in the region $16\,000\text{--}19\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, the band width spreading over $\sim 3\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggesting an octahedral environment around cobalt(II) ion in these complexes. The cobalt(II) inner complex salt is of low-spin type possessing magnetic moment of 2.1 B.M. The spectra showed a broad band at $20\,000\text{--}22\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with some amount of structure which manifests that cobalt(II) ion is placed in a square-planar ligand field. However, the high intensity of these bands arise probably due to charge transfer transition.

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